
MULTI-OBJECTIVE VOLTA ELECTRIC EEL OPTIMIZER: THE MATHEMATICAL MODELS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the mathematical models for a proposed Multi-Objective Volta Electric Eel Optimizer (MoVEO), a bio-inspired optimization algorithm designed to solve complex multi-objective optimization problems (MOPs) with conflicting objectives. MoVEO is developed by modeling the swarm intelligence and social predatory strategies of Volta Electric Eels. It incorporates principles of both biological and cultural evolution. These principles allow agents to communicate and share knowledge globally through a belief space, enhancing optimization efficiency. The algorithm will be tested on multi-objective benchmark functions to evaluate its robustness and effectiveness in handling MOPs and adapting to complex search environments. To validate its performance, MoVEO will be compared with widely recognized multi-objective algorithms, such as MOPSO, NSGA-II, MOEA/D, and SPEA2. This comparison will assess the algorithm's advantages and improvements over existing methods

Keywords: *Multi-Objective Optimization, Volta Electric Eel, Bio-Inspired Algorithm, Electrolocation, Cultural Evolution, Exploration And Exploitation Balance;*

INTRODUCTION

The nature has evolved and adapted strategies for many of the problems, leading to the development of more sustainable and effective solutions. Many real-world engineering problems are nonlinear, and solving them using conventional analytical methods is difficult [1], [2]. Optimization is a systematic approach to enhancing performance, reducing costs, and achieving feasible solutions for highly complex engineering and computational problems. The process of solving a MOP is known as multi-objective optimization (MOO) [5], [6]. The Multi-objective optimization problems (MOPs) have two or more conflict objectives, in which improving one objective leads to the degradation of the other [3], [4], [5]. The principles and inspiration of biological evolution in nature are the foundation of a new and competitive approach to solving optimization

problems. Bio-inspired algorithm is an emerging approach which is based on the principles and inspiration of the biological evolution of nature to develop new and robust competing techniques to solve optimization problems[7], [8], [9]. The importance of optimization in modern science and technology is crucial to the fact that many real-world problems are too complex to be solved by conventional methods, and optimization provides a systematic approach to finding the best solution[10], [11], [12].

The computational approach inspired by the process of cultural evolution observed in society is the cultural evolution strategy in the optimization process[13], [14]. The optimization process is guided by the Cultural Evolution Principles, which utilize human-like social and cultural behaviors to tackle complex problems[13], [15]. The cultural evolution strategy in optimization refers to a computational approach inspired by the process of cultural evolution observed in society[13], [15]. The fundamental principle is that knowledge develops within a population space is disseminated and refined over time, leading to socially coordinated behaviors that improve problem-solving efficiency[13], [15]. The Population Space, Belief Space, knowledge sources, Cultural Protocols, Dual Inheritance Systems, Emergent Social Structures and Problem-Solving Phases are the main elements that interact to simulate and enhance problem-solving processes by integrating principles from cultural evolution[13], [15]. Cultural evolution principles refer to the processes through which cultural knowledge, behaviors, practices, and technologies change and develop over time[13], [14], [15]. In optimization, these principles are applied to guide problem-solving by drawing inspiration from how human societies evolve and adapt culturally[14], [15].

The Biological evolution in algorithms utilizes mutation and crossover, the agents share information locally. However, cultural evolution allows agents to evolve and share information globally through a belief space, leading to faster evolution[13], [14]. This paper presents an innovative bio-inspired optimization algorithm called the Multi-Objective Volta Electric Eel Optimizer (MoVEO). This algorithm is inspired from the Swarm Intelligence (SI) and Social Predatory Strategy of Volta electric eels to solve complex, multi-objective optimization problems (MOPs). The integration of cultural evolution principles is the key innovation in MoVEO, to enable the algorithm to learn from past experiences and adapt dynamically to complex search environments. The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: MoVEO Cultural Evolution Framework is presented, section 2.2, Adaptive Strategies of

Volta Electric **Eel** is presented, by the mathematical models of MoVEO using cultural evolution strategy in section 3 and conclusion and recommendation in Section 4.

Cultural Evolution

MoVEO Cultural Evolution Framework

In MoVEO framework, the agents interact with their environment to solve multi-objective optimization problems. The key components stored in the Belief space include Normative and Situational Knowledge <ref>. The Agents interact with their environment and adjust their positions, frequency, and amplitude based on the knowledge they gain from the Belief space. The Agents' performance is evaluated based on prey capture success, energy efficiency, and diversity simultaneously. The top-performing agents are selected by the Selection mechanism, and their knowledge updates the Belief Space. The selected individuals' agents are the basis for generating new populations in the next iteration. The Belief space is constantly updated with new knowledge from the agents' performances, and this knowledge influences the agents' future actions. The (+OBJ) represents the prey capture success, energy efficiency and diversity. In the optimization process, the performance of each agent is measured against these objectives. The Fig1 illustrate the MoVEO Framework with key components, the Belief space, Selection, Influence and the agents that continuously interact.

Figure 1 MoVEO Cultural Evolution Framework

The MoVEO extends the basic MoVEO framework, and the optimization process incorporates the cultural influence, to guide the agents toward optimal solutions.

MoVEO Algorithm

The MoVEO begins by initializing a population of agents and a Belief Space constitutes cultural knowledge of normative, situational, and historical knowledge. Key parameters such as objective functions (prey capture success,

energy efficiency, diversity), the number of agents, and iterations are set. Agents are randomly assigned positions, frequencies, and amplitudes to start searching for optimal solutions. Their fitness is evaluated, and the Belief Space is updated based on the best-performing agents' knowledge. The algorithm then enters a main loop where agents' fitness is reassessed, top agents are selected, the Belief Space is updated, and a new population is generated to explore more promising areas. This cycle repeats until the maximum number of iterations is reached, ensuring continuous learning and refinement toward multi-objective optimization. Figure (2) is the the MoVEO cultural evolved pseudocode.

Figure 2 Cultural Evolved MoVEO pseudocode

Adaptive Strategies of Volta Electric Eel

The Volta's Electric Eel is a freshwater electroreceptors predator that has thousands of cells, the on the surface of the skin to store electricity. Electrolocation is a strategy that Volta Electric Eel utilize to sense and interpret electric fields in the environment using electroreceptors. In the natural environment generate low-voltage electric pulses to detect objects and high-voltage discharges to stun prey. The Volta Electric Eel utilizes electric signals in a sophisticated way to perceive their surroundings and coordinate their actions effectively using Electric Organ Discharges (EOD) signal. The Volta Electric eels can adjust the strength and frequency of their electric signals to convey the information. These signals coordinate movements and avoiding collisions. The collective sharing of positional and environmental information enhances the Swarm of Volta Electric Eel's ability to explore and exploit resources efficiently. The social predation, swarm intelligence, and cooperative hunting are a range of multi-dimensional strategies utilized by the Volta Electric eel for collective decision-making and adaptability in hunting for prey [18], [19], [20]. To explore the search space, and enhance adaptability and flexibility in optimization, the MoVEO mimics these principles by modifying strategies based on evolving conditions. The electric signals (EODs) for communication is adapted by the Volta Electric eel to navigate their environment, the MoVEO

mimics this communication strategy to enhance information exchange between agents. It enhances the exploration and exploitation of the search space [21].

The Volta Electric eels and the MoVEO exhibit a high success rate in capturing prey and finding optimal solutions respectively. The Volta Electric Eel are successful predators and exhibit high success in their natural environment to efficiently locate and capture prey using EOD signals [21], [22], [23]. To find optimal solutions to complex problems, the MoVEO efficiently explores possible solutions and selects the best ones, it mirrors the Volta electric eels' ability to identify and capture prey using an EOD signal [22], [23]. There is parallel coordination exhibited in Volta Electric Eel, the group makes decentralized decisions, and adjusts movements based on group coordination and their environment [19], [21], [24]. The MoVEO handles complex tasks efficiently utilizing parallelism, it uses multiple VEO agents, each exploring different parts of the search space independently. The Joint Avoidance Response (JAR) used by the Volta Electric eels ensures safe and stable navigation in their environment, similar to the MoVEO's approach to avoiding search space overcrowding and converging towards better solutions in a stable manner [22], [25], [26].

Multi -objective Volta Electric Eel Optimizer Evolution Framework

The electrolocation and hunting strategy of Electric Fish is mimicked by the Multi-Objective Electric Fish Optimization algorithm (MOEFO) to focus on balancing exploration and exploitation in a multi-objective optimization framework [16], [17]. The MOEFO algorithm is more focused on genetic evolution than cultural evolution, the individual agents evolve independently of one another without direct communication, it relies on biological evolution principles [13], [14], [16]. The agents focus on their local search without explicit communication between them and do not share knowledge directly. They depend on their fitness and performance [13], [14], [16], [17]. However, Multi-Objective Volta Electric Eel Optimizer (MoVEO) incorporates biological and cultural evolution (dual inheritance systems). In MoVEO, agents communicate and share knowledge through a process inspired by Volta electric eels' communication and cooperation. This leads to more sophisticated behaviors, such as jamming avoidance response and collective decision-making, enhancing overall optimization efficiency.

The MoVEO is an evolution of MOEFO, it incorporates more advanced concepts such as cultural evolution, agent communication, emergent social structures, and adaptive learning. These features make MoVEO more robust

and efficient for solving complex, multi-objective optimization problems. The MoVEO adapts a combination of electro-sensory feedback, dynamic adjustments in search intensity, real-time learning, and multi-objective optimization strategies. To effectively balance exploration and exploitation, avoid premature convergence, and optimize multiple conflicting objectives simultaneously the adaptive behaviors allow the algorithm, through its sophisticated adaptation mechanisms, MoVEO solves complex optimization problems efficiently in dynamic and uncertain environment. This paper focus on a detailed mathematical model that reflects the behaviors of the Volta Electric Eel to develop an efficient multi-objective optimization algorithm

B. Mathematical Models of the Cultural Evolution of MoVEO

a. Initialization

The MoVEO initializes the population dynamically in the search space to ensure exploration across a wide range of potential solutions, it then reduces the exploration to focus on fine-tuning solutions in promising regions. Normative Knowledge, Situational Knowledge, and Domain Knowledge are the three components that rule the movement of the agents in the MoVEO. The agent's position in the search space after the initialization phase are updated on a combination of these knowledge components The new position for an agent is influenced by its current position, the best solution found so far (normative knowledge), the current environmental conditions (situational knowledge), and its historical experiences (domain knowledge). The position update equation is represented by equation 1.

$$P_{i,j}(t + 1) = P_{i,j}(t) + \alpha \left(P_{best,i} - P_{i,j}(t) \right) + \beta \cdot S_j(t) + \gamma \cdot D_j(t) \quad (1)$$

Where:

$P_{i,j}(t + 1)$ is the updated position of VEO agent i in the Jth dimension at time t+1.

$P_{i,j}(t)$ is the VEO agent current position

α, β and γ are Coefficients that control the influence of normative, situational, and domain knowledge, respectively

The Evolution components of Population initialization

i. Normative knowledge

The convergence of the population toward optimal regions of the search space is facilitated with normative knowledge. It ensures that the VEO agents are influenced by good solutions and that they will gradually move towards

promising solutions. The normative knowledge component is represented by

$$\alpha (P_{best,i} - P_{i,j}(t)),$$

$P_{best,i}$ is the most promising solution found so far.

$P_{i,j}(t)$ is the current position of VEO agent i in the j^{th} dimension at time t .

α is a coefficient that controls the strength of the pull (influence) towards the best-known solution.

ii. Situational knowledge

The situational knowledge component adapts the agent's movement based on environmental factors, such as proximity to boundaries or constraints in the search space. It is represented by the component $\beta \cdot S_j(t)$.

$S_j(t)$ is a situational vector that reflects environmental factors in the i^{th} dimension at time t .

β is a coefficient that determines the influence of situational knowledge on the agent's position.

iii. Domain Knowledge

Domain knowledge leverages the agent's past experiences to guide future movements, encouraging agents to build on previous successes or avoid repeating past mistakes. It is represented as $\gamma \cdot D_j(t)$

$D_j(t)$ A domain vector representing the historical knowledge or past experiences of the agent in the j^{th} dimension at time t .

γ : A coefficient that controls the influence of past experiences on the agent's current position.

The domain vector of the historical knowledge or past experiences of the agent in the j^{th} dimension at time t .

Initial Frequency and Amplitude Initialization:

The VEO agents randomly generate the initial frequencies and biased towards culturally learned effective values, this improves the MoVEO's ability to explore the search space effectively. The initialization exhibits more intelligent characteristics by past performance through a layer of cultural learning and the influence of belief space. The equation 2 represents the initialization Frequency, that is randomly generated and values are influenced by historical, situational, and normative knowledge stored in the belief space.

$$F_{i,m} = F_{min,m} + rand(0,1) \times (F_{max,m} - F_{min,m}) + \beta(\alpha_s C_{s,m} + \alpha_n C_{n,m} + \alpha_h C_{h,m}) \quad (2)$$

Where:

$F_{min,m}$ and $F_{max,m}$ are the lower and upper bounds for the frequency of the m^{th} objective

$C_{s,m}$ is the Situational knowledge from the belief space for the m^{th} objective

$C_{n,m}$ is the Normative knowledge guiding preferred frequency ranges for the m^{th} objective.

$C_{h,m}$ is the Historical knowledge of the past performance trends for the m^{th} objective.

β , α_s , α_n , α_h are the weighting factors that control the influence of cultural knowledge.

$F_{i,m}$ is the sum of the adjusted random component and the knowledge-based adjustments of the frequency.

$$F_{min} = [F_{min,1}, F_{min,2} \dots F_{min,m}]^T$$

$$F_{max} = [F_{max,1}, F_{max,2} \dots F_{max,m}]^T$$

$$C_s = [C_{s,1}, C_{s,2} \dots C_{s,m}]^T$$

$$C_n = [C_{n,1}, C_{n,2} \dots C_{n,m}]^T$$

$$C_h = [C_{h,1}, C_{h,2} \dots C_{h,m}]^T$$

The diversity in frequency is obtained randomly, and the initial frequencies are biased toward values that have been effective in past iterations because of the cultural knowledge component. The effective ranges of frequency ranges from the belief space is the cultural knowledge and is referred to as the accumulated knowledge derived from the past experiences of VEO agents (solution) in previous generations of the MoVEO. The initialization of frequencies in the current population is the knowledge that is stored in the belief space. It reflects the frequency values of VEO agents that have historically led to successful exploration and exploitation of the search space for each objective.

Initialization of Amplitude

Influenced by past successes, learned norms, and historical trends the initial Amplitude is randomly assigned. The equation 3 represents the amplitude initialization.

$$A_{i,m} = A_{min,m} + rand(0,1) \times (A_{max,m} - A_{min,m}) + \beta(\alpha_s C_{s,m} + \alpha_n C_{n,m} + \alpha_h C_{h,m}) \quad (3)$$

Where:

$A_{i,m}$ is the amplitude value for the i^{th} VEO agent of the m^{th} objective. It constitutes a random component for diversity and exploitation based on past experiences stored in the belief space, it has a knowledge-based adjustment.

$A_{max,m}$, $A_{min,m}$ are the lower and upper bounds for the Amplitude of the m^{th} objective.

$$A_{min} = [A_{min,1}, A_{min,2} \dots A_{min,m}]^T$$

$$A_{max} = [A_{max,1}, A_{max,2} \dots A_{max,m}]^T$$

A_{min} is a vector containing the lower bounds for amplitude values for each objective.

A_{max} is a vector of the upper bounds for amplitude values for each objective.

$$C_s = [C_{s,1}, C_{s,2} \dots C_{s,m}]^T$$

$$C_n = [C_{n,1}, C_{n,2} \dots C_{n,m}]^T$$

$$C_h = [C_{h,1}, C_{h,2} \dots C_{h,m}]^T$$

Communication and Prey Detection:

The electric signals from Electric Organ Discharge (EOD) of Volta Electric Eel for navigation, detecting, locating prey, and underwater communication. For coordinating the swarm of Eels and guiding the search process, focusing on multiple objectives simultaneously, the communication strategy is required.

Broadcasting Signals:

Utilizing a communication mechanism each VEO agent shares information with its neighbouring agents regarding frequency, amplitude, and objectives information. The knowledge-based communication mechanism makes it to have more intelligent communication between VEO agents, The mechanism ensures that each agent's behaviour is guided not only by random exploration but also by learned strategies and patterns from previous experiences using

$$S_i^{bs} = \frac{1}{N_a} \sum_{j=1}^{N_a} \left(S_{i,j}^{agent} + \beta (\alpha_s C_{si,j} + \alpha_n C_{n,m} + \alpha_h C_{h,m}) \right) \quad (4)$$

Equation 4.

Where:

S_i^{bs} represents the broadcasted signal by an agent for i^{th} objective

N The total number of agents in the population.

$S_{i,j}^{agent}$ represents the signals that agent i^{th} share with its neighbouring j^{th} agent in the population.

$C_{si,j}$ represents the situational knowledge shared between agents.

$C_{n,m}$ represents the normative knowledge, guiding preferred behaviors or solutions between agents

$C_{h.m}$ is the historical knowledge, derived from the past performance trends or experience shared between agents.

$\alpha_s, \alpha_n, \alpha_h$ are the weighting factors that controls the influence of Knowledge-Based Adjustments.

β is a tuning parameter

The signal S_i^{bs} broadcasted by each VEO agent to its neighbouring agents constitutes a knowledge-based component derived from its belief space. The signal is influenced by situational knowledge (current state of the search), normative knowledge (objectives based on group dynamics), and historical knowledge (previous experience or trends observed in past generations of agents). The agents broadcast their present status and communicate with each other by taking into account the collective knowledge that has been gathered from past interactions. This contributes to better informed and efficient swarm coordination, improving the multi-objective optimization search process

Signal Distortion:

The distortion in Volta Electric Eel is either due to physical interference or noise in the water. The MoVEO accounts for signal distortion in the communication process, that can affect the quality of solutions., For the swarm to maintain effective optimization even in the presence of environmental challenges, the agents account for both the signal distortion due to physical interference or noise and the knowledge accumulated from belief space. The knowledge from previous iterations or experiences to mitigate or adapt to such distortions is represented with equation 5.

$$S_i^{bs} = \frac{1}{N_a} \sum_{j=1}^{N_a} \left((V_{i,j}^{agent} + \alpha \cdot \text{distortion}_{i,j}) + \beta (\alpha_s C_{s,i,j} + \alpha_n C_{n.m} + \alpha_h C_{h.m}) \right) \quad (5)$$

Where:

S_i^{bs} is the broadcasted signal emitted by agent i.

N_a is the total number of neighboring agents

$V_{i,j}^{agent}$ A vector containing information's strategy shared by agent i

$\text{distortion}_{i,j}$ is the signal distortion that occurs between agent iii and neighbouring agent jjj due to interference or noise.

$C_{s,j}$ the situational knowledge shared between agent i and agent j considering current environmental and objective-specific conditions.

$C_{n.m}$ are the normative knowledge guiding strategies for solutions, based on collective group preferences.

$C_{h.m}$ is the historical knowledge gathered from past interactions and trends, helping agents adjust based on previously successful solutions.

$\alpha_s, \alpha_n, \alpha_h$ are the weighting factors for situational, normative, and historical knowledge, respectively.

β is the scaling factor controlling the overall contribution of the knowledge-based adjustments. The accumulated knowledge stored in the belief space enables agents to become more effective at adjusting their communications under distorted conditions to improve the quality of solutions generated by the MoVEO.

Frequency and Amplitude Updates

The Volta electric eels adjust their electric signals by modulating frequency and amplitude to detect prey, navigate their environment, avoid collisions, and coordinate group behaviour. The strength and frequency of the Volta electric eel are adjusted to convey different types of information to coordinate movements and ensure effective group behavior. In the MoVEO algorithm, the frequency and amplitude of the VEO agents are updated based on multi-objective fitness values. These updates drive the exploration and exploitation processes in the search space, which are essential for achieving convergence to optimal solutions. However, the updates have become more intelligent and adaptive by integrating cultural evolution knowledge, including normative, situational, and historical knowledge. the agents can evolve their frequency and amplitude updates in a more sophisticated manner utilizing these Knowledge represented in Equation 6.

$$F_{(t)} = \alpha F_{(t-1)} + (1 - \alpha) \cdot \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N f_{mi} + \beta C_f + \delta S_f + \tau H_c \quad (6)$$

:

$F_{(t)}$ is the updated frequency of the i^{th} Volta Electric Eel agent at time t

$F_{(t-1)}$ is the frequency of the VEO agent at time $(t-1)$

α is the tuning parameter that controls the magnitude of the update and ensure that the frequency update does not become too large

C_f is the normative knowledge about the optimal frequency based on the collective behavior of past successful VEO agents.

S_f is the situational knowledge that adjusts the frequency based on the current environment

H_c is the historical knowledge about successful frequency ranges from previous iterations, helping agents avoid mistakes and focus on effective frequency strategies.

β, δ and τ are the factor that controls the influence of normative, situational, and historical knowledge on the frequency update.

The efficiency of communication, navigation, and prey detection of MOVEO is enhanced by the amplitude of the electric signals emitted by Volta Electric Eel. Based on the average multi-objective fitness values of the entire population the amplitude of VEO agents and the knowledge accumulated in the belief space regarding optimal amplitude values that have proven effective in previous search is updated using equation 7.

$$A_{(t)} = \alpha A_{t-1} + (1 - \alpha) \cdot \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N f_{mi} + \beta C_a + \delta S_a + \tau H_a \quad (7)$$

Where:

$A(t)$ is the updated Amplitude of the i th Volta Electric Eel agent at time t

A_{t-1} is the Amplitude of the VEO agent at time $(t-1)$

α is the tuning parameter that controls the magnitude of Amplitude update

f_{mi} is the fitness value for the m^{th} objective of agent i .

β, δ and τ are weighting factors that control the influence of normative, situational, and historical knowledge on the amplitude update.

C_a is the normative knowledge of the optimal amplitude, based on collective strategies from successful VEO agents.

S_a Is the situational knowledge, that adjusts the amplitude based on the current information and the environment

H_a is the historical knowledge from past generations, helps guide the amplitude update based on previous searches.

In the MoVEO, the agents can evolve their frequency and amplitude updates in a more sophisticated manner, with normative, situational, and historical knowledge. This combination of knowledge from the belief space allows for a more efficient and adaptive search process, enhancing the MoVEO's ability to converge on optimal solutions.

Prey Herding and Encirclement

The Volta electric eel exhibits a predatory strategy that increases hunting efficiency by herding prey into tightly packed formations and guiding them toward shallower water, This tactic limits the prey's movement and facilitates prey capture. The MoVEO mimics this behavior to efficiently navigate complex search spaces to ensure the VEO agents converge on optimal solutions within a search space. The VEO agents converge on optimal solutions by adopting strategies inspired by the biological strategy. However, the Cultural Evolution knowledge of normative, situational, and historical

knowledge integrated into the herding strategy exhibits more adaptive, intelligent, and efficient decision-making. This is represented in Equation 8.

$$X_r(t + 1) = X_r(t) + \beta \left(\frac{\nabla F(X_r(t))}{\|\nabla F(X_r(t))\|} + \gamma N_k + \delta S_k + \eta H_k \right) \quad (8)$$

Where:

$X_r(t + 1)$ is the updated position of the prey at time $(t + 1)$

$X_r(t)$ is the current position of the prey

β is a control coefficient for the strength of the herding strategy

$\nabla F(X_r(t))$ gradient vector of a multi-objective fitness function F

$\frac{\nabla F(X_r(t))}{\|\nabla F(X_r(t))\|}$ is the magnitude of the gradient vector

N_k Is the normative knowledge of the optimal herding behaviour of VEO agents based on collective learning from previous agents.

S_k is situational knowledge, adapts the herding strategy to real-time environmental factors

H_k is the historical knowledge from past experiences of herding to enhance current strategies

Shrinking Circle Mechanism

The Volta electric eels encircle the tetra of prey ball in a tightening formation as they get closer to the prey, reducing the prey's escape routes with focused attack. The strategy enables the Volta Electric Eel to concentrate on capturing the prey within a manageable distance. The MoVEO mimics the Shrinking Circle Mechanism of hunting and capturing of prey by Volta Electric Eel. The Shrinking Circle Mechanism is vital for focused exploration, enhancing the search efficiency near-optimal solutions. To make the search process more informed and efficient the shrinking circle mechanism is enhanced by the cultural knowledge from norms and past experience is represented mathematically in equation 9.

$$D = C(\|\nabla f_{prey_capture}\| \cdot \nabla f_{prey_capture} + \|\nabla f_{energy_efficiency}\| \cdot \nabla f_{energy_efficiency} + \|\nabla f_{diversity}\| \cdot \nabla f_{diversity}) + \gamma C_a \quad (9)$$

Where:

D is the distance between the Volta Electric Eel agents and the prey position.

C is a control parameter that scales the distance vector.

C_a is the cultural knowledge (normative, situational, and historical knowledge)

γ is the factor that controls the influence of cultural knowledge on the shrinking circle mechanism.

Collision Avoidance Response (JAR)

The Electric Organ Discharges (EOD) of Volta Electric Eel is utilized for communication and navigation of their environment. The Volta Electric eels convey various types of information, location, and identity, adapting to environmental changes utilizing electric fields in the water, and the modulation of EOD frequencies. The Volta Electric eels and the MoVEO evolve over time for efficient interaction, navigation, and adaptation to dynamic environments harnessing the key factor of cultural evolution, The electric fields overlap when two Volta electric eels with similar EOD frequencies are close to each other. This causes interference that results in the EOD signal's phase and amplitude modulation, the interferences impair Volta Electric's Eel ability to accurately sense distortions caused by objects or prey in the water. The jamming avoidance response (JAR) is an adaptive strategy of Volta Electric eel to mitigate the detrimental effects of the interference and its electrolocation capabilities. The Volta Electric Eels shift their frequencies to avoid "overcrowding" their search spaces with overlapping fields. The MoVEO ensures that VEO agents do not cluster excessively and maintain diversity in the population by incorporating collision avoidance responses. By shifting frequencies, eels avoid "overcrowding" their search spaces with overlapping fields. The MoVEO incorporates collision avoidance responses to prevent the VEO agents from clustering excessively. This adaptation reflects the accumulation of normative knowledge shared among Volta Electric eels for effective communication, the situational knowledge learned from real-time encounters with neighbouring eels, and historical knowledge from past experiences. This is represented in Equation 10.

$$F(t) = f(c) + (\gamma K_n + \delta K_s + \eta K_h) \left(\sin 2\pi f_c t + (\Phi + \Delta \Phi) \right) \quad (10)$$

Where:

$f(t)$ is the vector of modulated frequency of the VEO agent at a specific time t . It is frequency of Volta Electric organ discharge (EOD) affected by modulation.

$f(c)$ is the central frequency of the VEO electric organ discharge. It is the baseline frequency around which modulation occurs.

t is the time variant

$\Phi + \Delta \Phi$ is adjusted phase shift to avoid interference, based on real-time feedback and learned strategies.

Converge towards the direction of the best neighbour

The Volta Electric Eels utilize (EOD) electric signals to locate prey in favorable environment conditions, and the MoVEO mimics the hunting strategy. After collision avoidance, the VEO search agents converge towards the direction of

the best neighbors. The convergence improves the population's fitness, it leads to better exploration and exploitation of the search space. It enhances the ability to find optimal solutions in a dynamic environment. In a culturally evolved search mechanism, the VEO agents adjust their orientation based on the best neighbor's position and accumulated knowledge. This ensures more efficient, adaptive and informed search behavior, it is represented in Equation 11.

$$\frac{\delta\theta_i}{\partial t} = k^*(\theta_{best_i} - \theta_i) + \gamma k_{norm} + \delta k_{sit} + \eta k_{hist} \quad (11)$$

Where:

θ_i is the current orientation of the search agents for the i^{th} objective

θ_{best_i} is the orientation angle of the best neighbour

γk_{norm} is the influence of normative knowledge agents adjustment.

δk_{sit} Is the situational knowledge incorporated into the orientation adjustment

ηk_{hist} the agent's accumulated experience.

The combination influences of Cultural, Normative and Situational knowledge, enables the agents to converge towards the best neighbour. The agents adapt both current and historical data to make the search more efficient and informed.

CONCLUSION

The MoVEO algorithm demonstrates a powerful, bio-inspired approach to multi-objective optimization by integrating the natural behaviors of Volta Electric Eels with the principles of cultural evolution. The combination of normative, situational, and historical knowledge allows the algorithm to efficiently navigate complex search spaces, enhance convergence, and avoid premature exploitation. The adaptive communication mechanisms, prey herding strategies, and collision avoidance responses Mathematically modelled contribute to a robust and resilient search process, enabling the algorithm to solve dynamic and uncertain multi-objective problems. By mimicking the Volta Electric Eels' sophisticated behaviors, the MoVEO algorithm not only improves exploration and exploitation but also provides a framework for the development of more advanced bio-inspired optimization techniques to solve multi-objective optimization problems.

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